

Profiling of Filamentous Green Algae Bioindicator from simulated Rice Paddy Field Using Optical Characterization of Chromophoric Properties via UV - Vis Reflectance Spectrometer

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Various organisms are present in rice paddy fields, each playing significant roles in the ecological balance in most agricultural system. Among these organisms is the algae. This study aimed to profile the green algae present in a simulated rice paddy field in Los Baños, Laguna, Philippines. Specifically, it aimed to profile the pigments present in the green algae sampled. Using the Shimadzu 2600 UV-Vis spectrometer, the relative reflectance of pigments present in the green algae were profiled and compared the reference standard board. The reflectance values peaked between 500 nm to 700 nm showing the presence of four pigments namely chlorophyll a, chlorophyll b, phycoerythrin, and phycocyanin. These pigments play important roles in the food production. These pigments are responsible for the biological processes such as the photosynthesis.

Keywords— Green algae; UV-vis; spectrometer; algal pigments; chlorophylls; phycoerythrin; phycocyanin

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